

Edge Computing to Enable Front-End Data Processing Capabilities in Smart Agriculture and Forestry

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Abstract—As a typical branch of distributed computing, edge computing plays an important role by shifting the computation unit from centralized servers to the local network end, thereby reducing resource consumption and alleviating network load. It allows data to be processed locally upon acquisition, without relying on unstable or limited infrastructure, making it an ideal solution for rural and remote areas, particularly in agro-forestry scenarios. Furthermore, AI and machine learning (AI/ML) techniques offer promising capabilities for accurate identification and prediction. To achieve lower redundancy, enable on-demand data analytics and optimal decision-making, this paper focuses on two key areas: IoT data processing/filtering and imagery-based object recognition/counting, with the purpose of digitalization and automation in the field. The performance results prove that the proposed edge solutions effectively reduce unnecessary data volume, achieving a false positive rate of only 1.03% in data filtering tests and an 82% decrease in imagery detection tests. These solutions capture only the relevant information or objects, enabling accurate and in-depth analysis based on user needs.

Index Terms—Edge Computing, Internet of Things (IoT), Smart Agriculture, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Digitalization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Internet of Things (IoT) networks [1] hold great potential for smart agriculture by enabling the characterization of environmental data features from different perspectives. The deployment of IoT sensors ensures prompt measurement, enables remote monitoring, and facilitates cost-effective and sustainable crop management [2]. The deployment is notably suitable for smart agriculture and for forestry applications.

For remote environmental monitoring, IoT networks produce continuous streams of raw data within local infrastructures. Highly reliable backhauling networks are expected to ensure smooth transmission of raw IoT data streams to remote data centers, but current network deployments can hardly meet this requirement in rural areas. Lacking stable connectivity, IoT data transmission is increasingly dependent on storage units, posing challenges due to limited device capacity.

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As raw IoT data is continuously generated and accumulates over time, transferring all IoT data to centralized locations for processing can overload bandwidth-limited and intermittently connected networks, resulting in higher latency and reduced system reliability. To address this, edge computing helps by processing data locally and reducing the amount of data that needs to be sent through the entire network. Compared to remote data centers, edge devices are deployed densely and much closer to data sources, thereby reducing the heavy traffic load of data streams sent to the cloud.

The development of edge computing technologies can bring significant added value in smart agriculture and forestry [3], [4]. Edge computing is committed to processing data locally (i.e., at the front end, close to data sources), and only transmitting selected data features that are considered highly relevant to farming operations. Edge computing provides processed data instead of raw data for subsequent transmissions, which effectively avoids the transmission of redundant data over long distances and alleviates the network burden. Consequently, edge solutions ensure significant bandwidth and energy savings [5], contributing to lowered latency and reduced data volume while facilitating the remote monitoring of targeted objects in the field. Additionally, through the integration of AI/ML technologies, edge computing further enhances decision-making based on captured sudden changes, emerging trends and other data insights, allowing for intelligent prediction, alerting, and counting through the analysis of acquired IoT data.

Furthermore, edge computing approaches proposed in this paper enable various on-demand data processing ranging from close to far edge, to address different challenges such as IoT data filtering, image recognition and counting. With strong front-end processing capabilities, edge-enabled technologies can both monitor static environmental conditions and track mobile objects like vehicles and people. While the IoT network aims at bridging the connectivity needs in the field, edge computing enhances system-level feasibility by enabling front-end processing and on-demand communication, relieving unnecessary expenses and computational resources, shifting agriculture toward smart digital development with minimal

human intervention.

In this paper, we propose several technical approaches for processing data at the network edge, including data prediction, filtering, and compression from Section II to IV. Then, we present imagery segmentation using computer vision models and selective frame transmission based on imagery identification in Sections V and VI, respectively. Each section details the scientific methods, the deployment of edge devices for in-field testing, and the corresponding performance results. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper and highlights promising directions for future research in edge computing.

II. IOT DATA PREDICTION AT THE NEAR EDGE

A. Related Work

Toward reliable and efficient application of edge computing methods in agriculture and their integration with IoT networks, several works proposed AI/ML-based approaches [6] for efficient classification and accurate prediction.

Particularly, some papers [7] proposed to reduce the complexity of raw IoT data through KNN-based categorization using "Seaborn" library in Python [7], where the authors presented a two-dimension contour plot (i.e., correlogram) that revealed the distribution of categorized IoT data. The proposed approach allows to efficiently target on the most relevant data features before extracting them from the raw dataset, enabling on-demand data filtering based on observed value range of high-density data category. In addition, M.Yu et al. proposed a LSTM (i.e., the long short-term memory)-based temperature forecasting scheme targeted at high spatial-resolution weather predictions [8]. Based on historical data statistics acquired from weather stations, the authors have compared the RMSE (i.e., Root Mean Squared Error) of LSTM model with existing models to evaluate the accuracy on hourly prediction.

B. Simulation Setup for LSTM-based Temperature Prediction

For in-field monitoring of crops and microclimate conditions, a large amount of environmental data needs to be acquired in real-time. In this regard, LSTM algorithm is employed based on a feedback loop [9], allowing self-correct predictions based on time-dependent patterns captured from sensor's data readings. Across this feedback loop, the algorithm leverages error margin between real data and predicted data, allowing itself to quickly learn newly emerging dynamics, data trends while adjusting its weights accordingly. Additionally, through MaxMinScaler normalization [10] and appropriate neuron drop-off ratio, the algorithm minimized the dependency on unreliable neurons, significantly lowering the loss during the entire process. This process aims to avoid overfitting, thus providing refined decision-making. As a result, after fine-tuning key hyperparameters, subsequent predictions can be achieved with higher accuracy.

C. Simulation Results

The simulation result for LSTM-based prediction is presented in Figure 1. LSTM can provide a feedback loop to automatically adapt the prediction, following the readings of actual

Fig. 1. LSTM-based Auto-correction for Temperature Prediction based on IoT data readings (Variation & Overlaps exist: Orange=Actual; Purple=Predicted).

data sequences. The decision of either applying real data or predicted data depends on the following logic: 1) If the current error margin $|\text{real_data} - \text{prediction}|$ exceeds the maximum threshold of tolerance, real data will be taken as decision; 2) Otherwise, predicted data will be applied. Consequently, based on a pre-determined threshold, the algorithm allows to provide refined decision-making, closely capturing short-term patterns while improving overall accuracy at the same time. In general, LSTM is reliable for predictions but is resource intensive, data readings and storage are consistently needed which is notably challenging for IoT sensors with limited memory capacity.

III. DRIFT DETECTION & NORMAL DATA FILTERING AT INTERMEDIATE EDGE

A. Related Work

Toward reliable and efficient application of edge computing methods in agriculture and their integration with IoT networks, several works proposed AI/ML-based approaches [11] for efficient classification and accurate prediction, while others focused on studying automatized data filtering schemes [12] at the front end to enable reduced IoT data transmission (i.e., under predefined conditions) and energy saving.

In addition, Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) [13] is a statistical control method dedicated to real-time drift detection. Through a "warm-up" window, CUSUM initializes a fast set-up for data quality analysis, followed by continuous drift decision making for substantial data sequences according to a predefined drift

Fig. 2. End-to-end data flows showing the gateway’s role: detect-and-forward.

threshold. CUSUM facilitates the automatized process of capturing changes over time according to selected data features from IoT datasets. However, the historic dataset provided during the “warm-up” is essential in CUSUM algorithm and it “consumes” some data readings instead of making drift decisions directly. Additionally, the threshold is fixed value depending on drift occurrence frequency. Thus, the threshold value must fit well the observed data statistics. Otherwise, the drifts cannot be detected in expected frequency.

B. Implementation of Data Filtering at the Intermediate Edge

An intermediate-level edge computing approach is employed on Smart IoT Gateway to capture major changes from received IoT data and forward only drifted data with large change scales. Cumulative Summary (CUSUM) [13] is a statistical control algorithm which allows to detect and record all the qualified drifts according to the comparison with a given threshold upon sensitivity. CUSUM algorithm is able to provide real-time drift detection decisions based on historic data readings during a time window, making it notably suitable for consistent IoT data filtering, where only the obvious changes (e.g., temperature, humidity, etc.) need to be captured. Towards the goal of on-need data filtering, algorithm settings have been regularly adapted, notably including a predetermined threshold which controls sensitivity to drift scales, to achieve high reliability and high detection accuracy (i.e., to avoid false alarm and miss detection, respectively). Consequently, data filtering ratio is subject to the data quality of IoT dataset and sensitivity level.

The proof-of-concept test has been performed through the deployment of network components at two locations in Luxembourg, which are approximately 50 km apart. The connection between the smart IoT gateway and the server was established via VPN. The smart IoT gateway was connected to Internet using a LAN cable, while the server is co-located to receive and read the drifted data values sent from the gateway.

In the local network, IoT device performs regular measurements and sends it via LoRa protocol to the smart IoT gateway which is equipped with a LoRa concentrator. Then, the smart IoT gateway hosts the CUSUM-empowered data filtering, which determines if and which data needs to be sent to the server via a selected backhauling link. Upon receiving the data from the smart gateway, the co-located server dashboards both raw and drifted data, meanwhile facilitates the comparison with local data analysis results (i.e., tested according to identical raw data sequences) for cross-validation using the same data filtering approach.

As depicted in Figure 2, followed by a warm-up session where an initial historic dataset is provided for CUSUM function to learn and define a drift’s scale based on observed data statistics (e.g., mean, standard deviation, etc.), the smart gateway schedules the reception and re-transmission of arriving data sequences according to the value of cumulative sum. Firstly, the gateway aligns n received data into a data sequence, places them at the end of the historic dataset for drift detection. Secondly, the gateway transmits raw IoT data ($length = n$) and drifted data ($length \leq n$) to the server, with a dedicated counter being used to distinguish these two types of data in a specific data packet. Finally, the gateway updates the historic dataset by adding the latest n raw data into the end and removing the n oldest data from the beginning of the dataset, so that the CUSUM function can be ready for hosting the next-round calculation using an updated historic dataset.

As a conclusion, the gateway acts as an “intermediate filter” between IoT device and server, to process IoT data locally using the CUSUM algorithm, and to transmit only effective data (i.e., drifted data), rather than sending voluminous IoT data collected over time across the entire network. The CUSUM algorithm tracks the data statistics and makes decisions for detecting drifts, thereby triggering data filtering actions at gateway level. This intermediate edge approach combines a drift detection method with a conditional data filtering mechanism, efficiently reducing the volume of transmitted data.

C. Result of the Proof-of-Concept Test

As Figure 3 shows, an in-lab test has been implemented where the input data is a temperature data sequence, in addition to the historic dataset which stores experimental data as initial data readings. The algorithm calculates the cumulative sum value, and compare with the predefined threshold, to determine if a positive or a negative drift occurs (i.e., in green and yellow, respectively).

Fig. 3. CUSUM reflecting cumulative data trend (positive & negative) before/after the drifted point.

In Figure 3, before the temperature drops dramatically from 32 °C to 18 °C at 6th timeslot, the CUSUM value was steadily cumulated in a positive way from 3rd to 6th slot, showing consistent positive data trend. This situation lasts until the sudden decrease of temperature to 18 °C at 7th slot, which completely erases the positive trend, dragging the CUSUM value below the threshold. CUSUM restarts the estimation of data trend at the two data of 18 °C (7th and 8th slot), which are both determined as non-drifted. Then, at 9th timeslot, an abnormal data 0.1 °C is found, causing the negative CUSUM value to peak within a very short time. The temperature later increases back to 20 °C at but the 10th slot remains drifted due to the delayed effect of determining data trend over time.

Temperature	Data Packet ID	Counter (1000=Raw)	Gateway Time	Server Time Data Reception
24.9	21	1000	6/27/2025 16:16	6/27/2025 17:16
24.1	20	1000	6/27/2025 16:16	6/27/2025 17:11
25.5	19	1000	6/27/2025 16:16	6/27/2025 17:06
20.9	18	1000	6/27/2025 16:16	6/27/2025 17:01
25.1	17	1000	6/27/2025 16:16	6/27/2025 16:56
24.8	16	1000	6/27/2025 16:16	6/27/2025 16:51
24.1	15	1000	6/27/2025 16:16	6/27/2025 16:46
25.5	19	11	6/27/2025 16:16	6/27/2025 17:06
20.9	18	10	6/27/2025 16:16	6/27/2025 17:01
25.1	17	9	6/27/2025 16:16	6/27/2025 16:56
25.6	14	1000	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:41
20.9	13	1000	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:36
25.1	12	1000	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:31
24.8	11	1000	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:26
24.1	10	1000	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:20
25.6	9	1000	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:15
20.9	8	1000	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:10
25.6	14	8	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:41
20.9	13	7	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:36
25.1	12	6	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:31
25.6	9	5	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:15
20.9	8	4	6/27/2025 15:41	6/27/2025 16:10
25.1	7	1000	6/27/2025 15:06	6/27/2025 16:05
24.8	6	1000	6/27/2025 15:06	6/27/2025 16:00
24.1	5	1000	6/27/2025 15:06	6/27/2025 15:55
25.5	4	1000	6/27/2025 15:06	6/27/2025 15:50
20.8	3	1000	6/27/2025 15:06	6/27/2025 15:45
25	2	1000	6/27/2025 15:06	6/27/2025 15:40
24.9	1	1000	6/27/2025 15:06	6/27/2025 15:35
25.1	7	3	6/27/2025 15:05	6/27/2025 16:05
25.5	4	2	6/27/2025 15:05	6/27/2025 15:50
20.8	3	1	6/27/2025 15:05	6/27/2025 15:45

Fig. 4. Raw data and drifted data received at the server, thanks to the implementation of CUSUM algorithm on smart IoT gateway for data filtering.

Finally, a gateway-level test was implemented using the edge-enabled data filtering scheme. The CUSUM algorithm only outputs 0-1 decisions while the smart IoT gateway controls the data-filtering actions: it only forwards drifted data (accompanied by its raw data for comparison), while “locking” normal temperature data within the local network to reduce data volume transmitted through backhaul. In Figure 4, a counter was set on the smart gateway to distinguish the raw data ($length = 7$) and drifted data ($length \leq 7$). These two types of data were sent per sequence within the same minute, followed by an update process of historic set on the gateway to maintain the accuracy of subsequent calculations. The result indicates the successful transmission of three complete data sequences and related drift positions & values being indicated.

As a result, according to the statistics of gateway-level test, among 8395 raw temperature data, 6085 drifted data packets have been detected as compared to 6061 drifts in in-lab test, resulting in a false positive rate at 1.03%. In total, 2319 ordinary data packets (2310 packets in in-lab test) were filtered

with an overall data filtering ratio at 27.62%, over a total packets number of 8395 being transmitted. In conclusion, this approach enables data filtering at the gateway level, with a high detection rate and affordable error rate.

IV. RXRM FOR EDGE-EMPOWERED REMOTE OPERATIONS

A. Related Work

In addition to data filtering methods for statistical control of IoT datasets, industrial operations also require video data compression at the edge to ensure smooth transmission for remote expert control. Nokia’s Real-time eXtended Reality Multimedia (RXRM) solution enables immersive, low-latency 360° video and spatial audio transmission for industrial applications such as teleoperation, remote support, and situational awareness [14]. It combines Nokia’s 5G 360° camera and bandwidth-optimized software to stream only the field of view, significantly reducing data loads while maintaining visual and auditory fidelity. RXRM has been deployed in critical environments like underground mining, seaports, and energy infrastructure, where physical access is limited or hazardous [15].

This edge-enabled application leverages RXRM in forestry machinery to enable remote expert assistance: immersive video streams from the field are relayed to an off-site expert, who can guide the operator in real time. This model aligns with previous research on XR-supported maintenance and teleoperation. For instance, Rebol et al. [16] explored mixed-reality remote assistance with real-time annotations, while Nagy et al. [17] proposed AI-augmented XR interfaces for hands-free guidance in maintenance settings. Heo et al. [18] developed a flexible XR architecture (FlexR) that optimizes latency and processing across edge/cloud resources, which complements RXRM’s focus on bandwidth efficiency. Compared to mainstream alternatives like Microsoft Remote Assist (HoloLens), Real Wear, or AR-enabled mobile platforms (e.g., Vuforia Chalk), RXRM provides a higher degree of spatial immersion and contextual awareness—essential for complex and remote industrial environments. These prior works underscore the increasing role of XR in enhancing human-machine collaboration, particularly where safety, distance, and complexity are critical factors.

B. Deployment of RXRM and Compression of Video Streams

Edge computing can significantly enhance video streaming performance by processing data closer to the source, ultimately reducing latency and bandwidth usage. These video streams can be used to remotely guide the forestry machine operators, from remote location during thinning and logging operations. A remote expert supports the operator through end-to-end communication while viewing high-quality, 360-degree live video streamed from cameras mounted on forestry machinery. An edge server deployed on the machinery processes and optimizes the video stream based on available transmission bandwidth.

Fig. 5. RXRM video encoding technique.

To achieve this goal, Nokia’s real-time extended reality multimedia (RXRM) is deployed. Nokia’s RXRM software framework dynamically processes multimedia content.

At the core of RXRM’s functionality lies real-time, low-delay XR multimedia delivery. The system minimizes bandwidth consumption by transmitting only the portion of the 360° video that is relevant to the viewer at any given moment (Field of view). This approach dramatically reduces bandwidth usage without compromising visual fidelity. Traditional 360° video setups require extensive bandwidth, but RXRM reduces this need by as much as 90%. Figure 5 shows how the data reduction is performed using the RXRM software.

As shown in Figure 5, a gaze-aware VR encoder optimizes 360° video streaming by delivering high resolution only to the user’s field of view, unlike traditional streaming, which transmits the entire video sphere uniformly. The encoder tracks eye movements or head orientation using sensors in VR headsets, dynamically adjusting video quality based on where the user is looking. As the gaze shifts, the high-resolution area updates in real-time for a seamless experience. This technology is especially beneficial in bandwidth-limited environments like forests, reducing considerable data usage. It is well-suited for 5G and mobile applications, offering faster, low-latency streaming while maintaining high visual quality.

C. Results of RXRM Implementation Test in Forest Machinery

Fig. 6. Schematic & realistic deployment of edge server on forest machinery.

As a result of Edge-enabled Implementation for transmission of video streams using RXRM, Figure 6 shows the

Fig. 7. Results through forest deployment of edge-enabled RXRM solution.

schematic of the deployment where the RXRM edge computing server is deployed on the forest machinery. Both the Edge server and a camera are connected to an xG modem, the camera streams the 360 high quality 8K videos to the server, the server equipped with RXRM video encoders encodes the video and compress it for transmitting over the network. Figure 7 shows the results where processing at the edge server converts around 150 Mbps of 360 streams to required 19 Mbps and 2.5 Mbps, as based on available bandwidth profiles, which also highlights that the output could be adjusted based on available bandwidth either set by a network or available by the operator.

V. IMAGERY SEGMENTATION AND TREE COUNTING

A. Related Work

Forest monitoring and surveillance have increasingly embraced drone technologies, combining multi-spectral imaging, deep learning, and edge computing to address challenges such as biodiversity assessment, deforestation monitoring, vegetation health analysis, and early fire detection. UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) enable high-resolution spatial data collection across difficult terrains and large areas [19], making them ideal for forest ecosystems. Image segmentation and object detection models, particularly those based on the Mask R-CNN architecture, have been employed for delineating individual tree crowns, classifying tree species, and estimating biomass. For instance, Zhang et al. [20] applied Mask R-CNN for tree segmentation in forest imagery, enabling precise structural assessment. Similarly, Onishi and Ise [21] demonstrated accurate tree species classification from RGB UAV imagery using deep learning, making it notably suitable for monitoring forest biodiversity.

B. Leveraging Drone’s Imagery Data for Tree Counting

To enhance situational awareness in the forests, a robust forest monitoring framework has been developed, incorporating key technological components such as edge computing, 5G networks, and drone technology. This framework serves two primary objectives. First, it leverages images captured by

drones to assess the overall health of the forest, focusing on tree counting and forest density analysis. This allows for a detailed and accurate understanding of forest conditions over time. Second, the system is designed to provide real-time alerts for fire detection, enabling prompt responses to potential hazards.

Fig. 8. Schematic of Edge processor with deployed AI analytics.

The setup in Figure 8 shows the deployment methodology where a standalone 5G network is deployed near a forest with all-in-one solution including 5G gNB and 5G core. An edge server is deployed for real-time processing of the data. The drones connected to the 5G network sends real time images and videos of the forest which are processed on the Edge to provide forest health parameters and also sends alerts to emergency personnel in case of fire detection. This facilitates real-time local processing and transmits only the key updates.

C. Performance Metrics Analysis of Image Segmentation

Fig. 9. Segmentation of the image from drone to count number of trees.

Particularly, the edge server is equipped with computer vision models. A comprehensive suite of deep learning models is implemented which is designed to operate on edge enablers, facilitating real-time detection and monitoring of the forest. The initial model is an image segmentation deep neural network designed to perform precise image segmentation on each frame captured by the multispectral camera mounted on the UAV. This process involves dissecting the image frame into enclosed pixel areas (blobs as shown in Figure 9) with

consistent colour and texture attributes. The color data of each identified segment can be used to effectively detect fire and smoke. This segmentation model is based on the widely adopted Mask RCNN paradigm used in RGB image segmentation. However, it is fine-tuned with innovative unsupervised domain adaptation methods to effectively process aerial multispectral images. Moreover, the second model is an object detection neural network that excels at recognizing various tree species within aerial imagery frames. By employing this model, the system generates bounding boxes that precisely encapsulate each tree identified in images captured by the UAV’s multispectral camera. This information is used to estimate the extent of thinning or deforestation required for specific forest locations.

The performance metrics refer to the accuracy and efficiency of the computer vision (CV) model in processing data, particularly the ratio of correctly predicted tree counts to the total predicted counts. For tree counting, the achieved performance can reach up to 82%, while the service deployment is limited to only 27 seconds. Additionally, the images are processed to effectively detect the presence of smoke or fire, with the model achieving up to 98% accuracy. This allows the edge server to promptly report the location of smoke or fire and send notifications to emergency personnel.

VI. IDENTIFICATION OF FIELD OBJECTS AND SELECTIVE TRANSMISSION OF FRAMES

A. Related Work

In addition to tree detection from drones’ images, cost-effective detection models in the agricultural fields have also been investigated. Recent advances in lightweight deep learning architectures have enabled efficient real-time object detection on low-power edge devices. Models such as SSD with MobileNet-v2 backbone have proven effective in scenarios where computational and energy resources are limited, making them suitable for embedded deployments in rural or agricultural environments [22]. Huang et al. [23] provided a comprehensive evaluation of object detectors on mobile hardware, confirming SSD-MobileNet’s strong balance between accuracy and speed. This has encouraged its adoption in smart agriculture and remote monitoring systems, where real-time inference is required without relying on continuous cloud connectivity.

Contoli et al. [24] introduced a power-aware multi-object tracking framework on Jetson Nano using SSD-MobileNet combined with IoU-based tracking and adaptive frame rate management (DIPM), achieving energy-efficient tracking with maintained accuracy. These works validate SSD-MobileNet-v2’s suitability for agricultural edge applications supporting our system’s core detection and tracking technology. Zhang et al. [25] proposed a power-aware vision system for real-time SSD-MobileNet detection with IoU-based tracking on Jetson Nano, demonstrating energy-efficient yet accurate object ID tracking in crop rows. These studies aligns closely with our deployment using confidence-tuned trackers and selective image reporting

enabling persistent multi-class detection over time with minimal bandwidth and power consumption.

B. Implementation of Edge-enabled Detection and Field Test

Edge-enabled imagery detection solutions are implemented. In Serbia, we employed Nvidia Jetson as edge device to enable periodical data transmission to Azure IoT Hub, with only captured frames of targeted objects being stored. In Norway, we applied CV model based on imagery data acquired from UAVs, enabling tree calculations and fire/smoke detection in forestry scenarios.

Toward the objective - securing crops and equipment, smart cameras have been deployed across two rural sites to monitor field activities and detect suspicious or hazardous behaviors that could threaten crops. Three edge-enabled smart camera systems are deployed at two locations in Serbia: one in Gospodjinci (Edge 1 - empowered by Jetson Nano 2GB) and two in Ćurug (Edge 2 - empowered by Jetson Nano 4GB). During continuous stream processing, the system actively detects objects of interest (e.g., person or vehicles) in the field. Each time a new object is detected, a unique ID is assigned to it and added to a recognition list. This ID is continuously tracked as long as the object remains in the scene and is removed once the object is no longer present.

To optimize storage and transmission efficiency, only the first frame in which a new object is detected is stored and transmitted to Azure Blob Storage. Subsequent frames or video sequences are not retained. Instead, a Jetson summarizing the detected objects over the previous five minutes is generated and transmitted to the Azure IoT Hub. This approach ensures that only essential data is stored while still providing a continuous record of detected activity.

For instance, if an individual enters the scene and stays for 15 minutes, the system will generate at least three Jetson transmissions reflecting their presence. However, only the first detected frame of that person will be stored as an image. If another person joins the scene, the Jetson transmission will be updated to indicate the presence of two individuals, and a new image will be sent when the second person is first detected. This process minimizes unnecessary data transmission while ensuring that significant events are recorded. Furthermore, if an individual leaves and later re-enters the scene, they are treated as a new detection, and a corresponding image is transmitted upon re-entry.

The monitoring process follows a structured workflow, as illustrated in Figure 10, which presents a diagrammatic representation of the data flow from the smart camera to the edge device, and subsequently to the Azure IoT Hub and Azure Storage. This figure visually depicts how objects are detected, processed, and selectively transmitted within the system.

C. Test Results for Detection Accuracy of Captured Frames

For camera monitoring system deployed in Serbia, each camera captures frames at a minimum rate of 15 FPS, meaning that every minute, a single stream collects approximately 900 frames. However, instead of storing all captured frames, the

Fig. 10. Periodical Upload of Statistical Data and Storage of Frames.

system selectively retains only those relevant to the detected activity. This selective storage approach optimizes storage and processing resources, preventing unnecessary data accumulation while maintaining a reliable record of detected objects.

The system focuses on detecting specific objects of interest, primarily people and vehicles. Within the vehicle category, the system further distinguishes between bicycles, cars, motorcycles, trucks, and buses, allowing for a more detailed breakdown of traffic patterns and scene analysis, as shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 11. Recognition of different types of objects from camera frames.

Every five minutes, statistical data is transmitted to Azure IoT Hub. This includes a cumulative count, which represents the total number of detected objects within that time frame, as well as a class-specific breakdown, which categorizes each detected object type. It is worth mentioning that the statistical data is transmitted to the Azure IoT Hub regardless of activity levels within the scene. However, frames themselves are transmitted selectively, with only those containing new or unique detected instances being sent to Azure Storage.

Overall, the proposed edge-based detection system achieved an average precision of 90.6% and recall of 84.5%, a false positive reduction of 82% through confidence threshold tuning

and selective class filtering, while maintaining real-time performance above 15 FPS and reducing frame transmission, ensuring efficient and accurate monitoring in rural environments. This approach minimizes bandwidth and storage requirements without compromising detection reliability, making it well-suited for low-connectivity environments. The system's adaptive data strategy, which transmits only statistical summaries every five minutes and selectively uploads frames containing novel detections, reduced the data load significantly: less than 1 in 10,000 frames were stored (less than 0.01% of all captured frames), with only 323 frames transmitted out of more than 3.6 million processed during the monitoring period. Performance improved notably over time, with decreasing rates of false positives and false negatives, particularly after refinements in tracking logic and classification settings. While occasional data transmission gaps were linked to hardware interruptions or power issues, overall system stability increased. These results underscore the system's value for rural deployments: offering reliable object detection, low transmission overhead and efficient edge processing in low-connectivity environments.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a wide range of edge computing approaches in agriculture and forestry. These approaches leverage the front-end capabilities of edge devices to enable real-time analytics, filtering, prediction for IoT data, and high-precision detection, counting for imagery data. Performance results show that our tests achieved 98.9% accuracy in data filtering and stabilized the false positive rate of imagery detection, resulting in a remarkable 82% decrease within 6-week test period. In the future, we aim to define specific strategies to trigger data processing schemes according to the user needs, as well as nature and quality of captured data, with an objective of achieving an optimized data reduction rate.

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